

Students, teachers and principals' views on the effects of school gyms on functioning of school

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Abstract. In this study, the views of students, teachers, and principals on the effects of gyms in schools on functioning of school were sought. The research is based on views of principals and teachers working in schools with gyms in Manavgat during the 2021-2022 academic year and students studying in these schools. The research was designed in qualitative descriptive phenomenology. Semi-structured interview forms were used to collect the research data. According to the findings of the research, it can be said that the school principal, students, and teachers had a positive perception of the gym in schools. In line with the results, it was suggested that all schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education should have gyms and that the physical capacity of the gyms in these schools should be increased.

Keywords: School gyms, students, principals, teachers

Introduction

The importance of sports and physical education courses in our lives is quite wide. The most important benefit of sports and physical education courses in our lives is physical health. Sports and physical education play an important role in maintaining and improving our physical health. Exercising regularly supports muscle and bone health, increases cardiovascular endurance, and reduces the risk of many chronic diseases such as obesity, heart disease, and diabetes. It also contributes to the development of basic physical abilities such as mobility, flexibility and balance. At the same time, sports and physical education have positive effects on our mental health. Exercising reduces stress, improves mood, and helps prevent mental health problems such as depression and anxiety. In addition, sports activities increase self-confidence, improve self-discipline, and improve learning capacity and cognitive functions (Bailey, 2004; Kılıç, 2015).

People who do sports not only grow socially, but also have more positive effects socially and mentally, as well as physical and mental benefits. Bad habits are the biggest problem for individuals and parents today, but doing sports creates a protective shield by preventing the formation of bad habits (Erbaş, Göral, & Kalemoglu 2016). Today's popular sports are considered divided into social, mental, physical and material areas. Additionally, while sports positively affect people's emotional states, they also contribute to their physical development. Doing sports helps the person to see the limit of what they can do, to recognize their essence and to do something by revealing their talents and creative areas with this definition. Without discriminating as a person or a team, doing sports helps interaction between individuals by reaching team spirit in teamwork. By multiplying their friendship areas, people who are in harmony with life together can thus be together. They can use their free time as effectively and efficiently as possible and help them develop in many other areas. The desire to win in sports is more of a balancing act than a bad competition. While this positive competitive environment has a positive effect on people's lives, it plays a positive role in the interaction between people by reducing the limitless wants

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and desires in their social environment. (Karataş, 2019). In addition to all these, since sports are universal, doing sports will teach people to be respectful, loving and understanding in response to people living in different geographies by changing the perspective of individuals and changing their perspectives

Sports contribute to the development of social skills through team games and group activities. Team sports help to acquire skills such as collaboration, leadership, communication, and problem-solving. In addition, sporting events and competitions encourage the formation of friendships between people and strengthen social relationships. In addition, sports and physical education teach discipline and the discipline of learning. Sports activities require regular training and preparation (Yaylacı, 2007). This provides students with important skills such as time management, responsibility, and goal setting. At the same time, sport emphasizes the importance of working for success, accepting failures, and continuous improvement. Therefore physical education in schools is useful for adopting a healthy lifestyle and staying active throughout life. These classes teach students the importance of playing sports and incorporating physical activity into their daily routine, helping them to lead a healthy life in the future (Arıcı, 2004). Thus, the importance of sports and physical education courses in our lives is of importance as doing sports supports our physical and mental health, contributes to our social and skill development, teaches discipline and learning discipline, and ensures the formation of healthy lifestyle habits.

In the study, it was aimed to interpret the views of principals, teachers and students on the effects of gyms in schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education on students, teachers, principals and the general functioning of the school. In addition, it is important to understand the views of students, teachers and principals who have a gym in their school regarding the effects of the gym on students, teachers, principals and the general functioning of the school, to understand how the gyms are perceived by the students, teachers and principals who use them, and to reveal the benefits of the gyms by the users.

The problem statement and sub-problems of the research were expressed as follows:

Problem Statement

What are students, teachers and principals' views on the effects of gyms in schools on functioning of the school?

Sub-Problems:

1. What are students, teachers and principals' views on gyms?
2. What are students, teachers and principals' views on the effect of teaching the physical education course in the gyms on the efficiency of the course?
3. What are students, teachers and principals' views on the effect of the use of gyms in terms students' behaviors on the courses other than physical education class?
4. What are the principals' positive or negative views on the attitudes and behaviors of the students who use the gym?
5. What are students, teachers and principals' views on the effect of gyms on school success?
6. What are students, teachers and principals' suggestions for more efficient use of gyms?

Methodology

Method and paradigm of research

The research was qualitative and a descriptive phenomenology design was used in the research. Qualitative research is a method that analyzes research questions with an interpretive approach (Lincoln

& Guba, 1985, Gunbayi & Sorm, 2018). Each phenomenon or event that is the subject of the study is in its own context and the meanings that people attribute to them are interpreted. Thus, the aim of the phenomenological study is to find out the essence of participants' perception of lived experiences (Creswell, 1998; Patton, 1990).

Sampling

The population of the study consisted of 7 principals and 230 teachers working in schools with gyms in Antalya Manavgat and 3435 students studying in these schools. The sample of the study consisted of 4 principals, 6 teachers (3 Physical Education teachers and 3 teachers in different branches) and 9 students selected by convenient sampling, (Table 1.)

Table 1. Information about principal and teacher participants

Participant	Age	Gender	Branch	School of Work
P1	45	Male	Manager	High school
P2	40	Male	Manager	High school
P3	37	Male	Manager	High school
P4	49	Woman	Manager	High school
T1	40	Male	Science	High school
T2	32	Woman	Visual Arts	High school
T3	30	Male	Math	High school
T4	39	Woman	Physical education	High school
T5	42	Male	Physical education	High school
T6	45	Male	Physical education	High school

Data collection

The study data were obtained by using the semi-structured interview form, which was finalized after the pilot interviews, and a theoretical framework created based on the literature review. With semi-structured interview forms, the views of principals and subject teachers working in high schools and the students on the effects of school gyms on functioning of the school were recorded with interviews conducted with 30-45 minute interviews in order to find answers to sub-problems.

Ethics statement

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 15 decision numbered 312 on September 8th, 2022, formal permission was obtained from the Antalya Provincial Directorate of National Education for the research numbered E-98057890-605.01-61022341 on October 17th, 2022, an informed consent form was obtained from the participants before the interview and participants were informed that their names would not be mentioned and be given the alphabetical codes for principals as P1, P2, P3, P4, for teachers as T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6 and for students S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, S8 and S9.

Rigour

In order to get validity and reliability criteria of a qualitative research, it is considered appropriate to use internal validity (credibility), external validity (transferability) and inner reliability (confirmability) and outer reliability (dependability) criteria (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In order to ensure the internal validity of the study, semi-structured interview form was finalized after the pilot interviews and a theoretical framework of the interview form was created based on the literature review. In order to ensure the external validity (transferability) analytical generalization was made to a theory in discussion. In order to increase the internal reliability (dependability) of the research, all of the findings was given without comment. In addition, the consistency rate (Kappa Value) was calculated as .083, almost perfect

agreement by comparing the codes by the researcher and a second person (Landis and Koch 1977). In order to increase the external reliability (dependability) of the research, the researchers ensured to present on demand all the data collection tools, raw data, coding during the analysis phase, and the perceptions, notes, writings and inferences that form the basis of the report to an expert other than the project team (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Gunbayi, 2018).

Data analysis

In the study, descriptive analysis was carried out, the results were presented with a descriptive manner and verbatim quotations were included, the findings obtained within the framework of the emerging themes and patterns were classified in line with the research objectives by using a qualitative software Nvivo 10 (Kelle, 1995; Cohen, Mannion, & Morrison, 2007).

Findings

1. Students, teachers and principals' views on gyms

The statements by the participants on gyms were examined according to school principals, students and teachers. All of the statements of principals were positive (f=4), the statements of eight of the students were positive (f=8) but one was negative (f=1) and the statements of five of the teachers were positive (f=5) but one was negative (f=1).

The views of some of the principal participants are given below:

I think gyms are extremely important for education. I think sports are essential for raising healthy generations. In this case, I think that the presence of gyms in schools will have a positive effect (P3).

I think there should be gyms in every school, even in every neighborhood. Especially in the basic education section, the benefit of gyms is very clearly seen (P4).

The views of some of the student participants are given below:

It's a social place, a space where you can show off your talents. We are able to show most of our talents in the gym, my perception of the gym is positive (S4).

It is much better for us to have a gym, because as a science high school student, our classes are predominant. Therefore, we need places and spaces where we need to relieve stress. Therefore, we can use it effectively in gyms. That's my perception, it's good.(S7)

The presence of gyms in schools also increases the contribution of students to their courses. Because we can go and socialize with our friends in our free time, we can attend courses better with a relaxed head because we socialize (S9).

The views of some of the teacher participants are given below:

Of course, gyms have a positive perception for us teachers, especially in schools, as they offer a fun learning environment and as a result, they provide efficient learning (T1).

In schools with gyms, gyms are very valuable in terms of children's development and the diversity of their physical activities. Unfortunately, there are very few gyms in our district, I think that schools with halls and gyms are very lucky, I think it is beneficial for the development of children (T4).

My thoughts towards gyms are positive. In fact, I believe that every school should have gyms as much as possible, starting from kindergarten. ...In addition, public gyms should be built in certain areas in the neighborhoods, where children can discover themselves, young people can do sports and relax, and people who are close to the point of being old can do sports in terms of exercising their bodies and there should be a gym that can be in the neighborhoods. Yes, the cost is very high, but let's say I think it is thought that two or three can be done on the basis of our district (T6).

When participants' views on gyms were examined in general, it can be said that almost all of the participants had positive views about the gym. It was found that only one student and one teacher had negative views on gyms.

2. The effect of teaching the physical education course in the gyms on the efficiency of the course

The statements by the participants on the effect of teaching the physical education course in the gyms on the efficiency of the course were analyzed according to principals, students and teachers. All of the statements of principals (f=4), students (f=9) and teachers (f=6) were positive.

The views of some of the principal participants are given below:

Physical education courses are taught more easily in gyms, students' motivation becomes more efficient, and the perception that many sports trainings are carried out in different branches according to the capacity of the hall is revealed (P1).

It is a 100% efficient area because our physical education teachers carry out the course work they do for our students during their courses by using our halls at the maximum level, so I think it increases productivity by 100% (P2).

The views of some of the student participants are given below:

Thanks to the hall, we develop our skills and try to take them to the top. Thanks to our teacher, he helps us (S4).

Since almost all kinds of sports equipment are materials and equipment in gyms, it benefits us both as a place to do the desired sports in physical education class and in terms of avoiding weather events, which indoor gyms provide. And for its efficiency, we can easily do the sport we want because it has all kinds of tools (S7).

Of course, as with any course, if we are studying biology, if a biology laboratory is required, then a gym is mandatory for physical education. From my point of view, this allows us to use it better and more effectively for physical education and to deal with various areas. Since the gym gives enough space, it is processed more easily and effectively. (S8).

The views of some of the teacher participants are given below:

Especially in unfavorable weather conditions, the presence of a gym provides convenience to us in terms of Physical Education course. In addition, having team branches such as volleyball and basketball in the gym provides an additional advantage for us. At the same time, I think that when students study in the gym, they are better motivated and more productive (T1).

I think it's a really good thing in terms of putting the theoretical training in the physical education class into practice, and I see gyms as a place where talents emerge (T5).

Of course, having a hall is a big advantage. Our materials are ready, our lines are ready, there are all kinds of conveniences. It's much easier to get kids motivated (T6).

When participants' views on the effect of teaching the physical education course in the gyms on the efficiency of the course were examined in general, it was found that all of the participants had positive views on the effect of teaching the physical education course in the gyms on the efficiency of the course.

3. The effect of the use of gyms in terms students' behaviors on the courses other than physical education class

The statements by the participants on the effect of the use of gyms in terms students' behaviors on the courses other than physical education class were examined according to principals, students and teachers. All of the statements of principals were positive (f=4), the statements of five of the students were positive (f=5) but four negative (f=4) and all of the statements of teachers were positive (f=6).

The views of some of the principal participants are given below.

As I just mentioned, our other teachers also do other activities in the hall in addition to physical education courses in my classes. They also receive positive feedback from our children from these activities. When we look at the characteristics of our school and the characteristics of our students, we also use our hall for our children's social activities, entertainment and games. Therefore, we always receive positive feedback in our hall. There is no negativity (P2).

In this regard, the use of gyms by our students both in physical education classes and in free hours prevents our students from some negative behaviors. Since they give their energy to sports, we can prevent some bad habits in this regard. At the same time, I think that there is a different motivation in other classes after the activity held there during the day (P3).

The positive views of some of the student participants are given below.

It's nice when we use the gym outside of class, it relieves our boredom and I find it positive in this respect (S5).

On the positive side, if you're the user, you can spend your time fun and useful in any way you want (S7).

The negative view of one of the student participants is given below.

They're causing discomfort by misusing the hall. Sometimes there is a lot of noise, they hit the basketball inside, even though it is forbidden. They can cause some discomfort when we don't have a teacher, but they can't do that when there is a teacher (S4).

The views of some of the teacher participants are given below.

If you ask as all schools, of course, it reflects positively, because our children cannot use their energy at home because our age is the age of technology. At least in physical education classes, we try to get rid of them a little bit so that our children can move at least a little bit and become aware of their skills (T3).

After teaching the physical education course in the gym, our students have the chance to learn and play more comfortably in the gym, of course, so when they enter other classes, they put us in an advantageous situation and make our students ready to learn (T4).

So friends have positive thoughts. Our children who play sports are more successful, more respectful, and feel more connected to the school (T6).

When participants' views on the effect of the use of gyms in terms students' behaviors on the courses other than physical education class were examined, all of the principals and teachers stated that the students' use of the gym had a positive effect on student behavior. But while five of the students said

that the students' use of the gym had a positive effect on student behavior, four of them said that it reflected negatively on student behavior.

4. Positive or negative views on the attitudes and behaviors of the students who used the gym

The statements by the participants on positive or negative views on the attitudes and behaviors of the students who used the gym were examined according to principals, students and teachers. All of the statements of principals were positive (f=4) the statements of seven of the students were positive (f=7) but three negative (f=3) and the statements of teachers were three positive (f=3) and three negative (f=3).

The views of some of the principal participants are given below.

The development of sports awareness in the students who use the gyms makes an important contribution to the school administration. We see that it has a positive effect on the behavior of the students who use the halls in terms of fulfilling their responsibilities and improving their behavior (P1).

We have stated that the students who use the gym have internal discipline. There are many positive aspects, and the negative aspects can sometimes cause accidents. A little more precautions need to be taken in this regard, it is a little difficult to control. I think that having a responsible person at the head of the students who play sports will eliminate these problems (P4).

The positive views of some of the student participants are given below.

Students use the gym when their classes are free, so I find it positive. And they use it very regularly. But I find it even more productive for some students to use the gym by doing sports instead of having fun (S5).

Positively, most of the students are responsible and they don't have any negative behavior, no harm to other students or the gym. In other words, I did not see any negative activity or attitude in this way (S7).

The negative view of one of the student participants is given below.

Students who use the gym are damaging the walls of the gym, it's not good for them to damage it. I think they should be more careful when they do activities in the gym (S6).

The views of some of the teacher participants are given below.

In schools with gyms, due to the financial conditions of the children, they have to come with all kinds of shoes during the course, so the wear and tear of the hall is a little too much, we can look at it negatively. Children may come to the gyms in places where the social and cultural structure is good with spare shoes, but since this is not suitable for the physical conditions and social environment conditions of the students in our school, they may have a negative opinion about this issue. On the other hand, we have always received the support of your school administration about the hall, we thank them. (T4).

My observations are that while there is a positive development in general, I think that only students should be made aware of the use of tools and inventories and how to use them in relation to the environment, for example, in terms of not polluting the environment (T5).

When participants' positive or negative views on the attitudes and behaviors of the students who use the gym were examined, all of the principals expressed positive views about the attitudes and behaviors of the students who used the gym and most of the students' views were positive except three. While half

of the teachers stated that the use of the gym reflected positively on the attitudes and behaviors of the students, and half of them said that it reflected negatively on them.

5. The effect of gyms on school success

The statements by students, teachers and principals on the effect of gyms on school success were examined according school principals, students and teachers and all of the statements of principals(f=4), students (f=9) and teachers(f=6) were positive.

The views of some of the principal participants are given below.

Having gyms contributes to the positive outlook of the student. The development of sports education in the halls also contributes positively to the success of the students in their academic courses. Because with the education students receive here, they become aware of taking responsibility and fulfilling their duties. We also see that they perform more behaviors that will contribute to their academic development in the future (P1).

It has a very positive impact on the school's success, especially its academic success. Here we see that we are a science high school, children who do sports are really different from others and they come to much better points. You see that the child plays football very well, plays basketball or table tennis very well; at the same time, the child achieves tremendous academic success. I had a student who was playing football very well, for example, he ranked 610th in Turkey in YKS in the university exam, we have students who are in the top thousand who are successful in table tennis and are academically successful. Sport definitely has a positive impact on academic achievement (P4).

The views of some of the student participants are given below.

If we think about sports success in gyms first, we can perform and achieve sports success against other schools in school sports because we can work thanks to the gym. Apart from that, in terms of academic success in school success, when we do sports, we can focus on the course because it develops our brain as a social activity and we can spend our time fun because we are not bored, we do not get distracted. That's why we are able to achieve academic success in a more focused way (S7).

I think it has a positive impact on our school success. Because, according to a scientific study, we can focus better because people who do sports have higher happiness hormones. Therefore, since such a field is also given, it affects our courses well, because we need to relieve stress (S8).

Since students who use the gym are physically healthier and mentally more vigorous, it positively affects school success (S9).

The views of some of the teacher participants are given below.

I mean, when you say school success in schools with gyms, you know, in the academic sense or in the other sense? As I said at the beginning, since children are now in the age of technology, children are at least discharging some of their energy because they are sitting still at home, and I think this energy discharge makes it easier for children to study while sitting. In other words, it has an impact on your academic success, because in individual sports, especially in team sports, what it means to be a team, what it means to enjoy individual success, this is reflected in your other courses (T3).

I really think that gyms have a 100% positive effect on the student's motivation in all subjects and their determination and willingness to study all subjects and their success in all subjects (T5).

When we consider the development of children as a process, it is not only academically; we also care about their social and cultural sports achievements. In my own opinion, I think that children in schools with gyms are more interactive with other subjects and contribute more to their development (T6).

When students, teachers and principals' views on the effect of gyms on school success were examined, all of the school principal, students and teachers stated that the effect of the gyms on school success was positive.

6. Suggestions for more efficient use of gyms

The suggestions for more efficient use of gyms by the participants were examined according to principals, students and teachers. For principals increasing the usage time of the gym (f=2), increasing the physical capacity of the gym (f=1), having sufficient personnel in the gym (f=1) were sub-themes, for students: increasing the usage time of the gym (f=4), increasing the number of sports competitions (f=2), increasing the adequacy of gym equipment (f=2), increasing the cleanliness of the gym (f=1) and for teachers increasing the usage time of the gym (f=3), increasing the physical capacity of the gym (f=1), having sufficient personnel in the gym (f=1) and increasing the gym equipment (f=1).

The views of some of the principal participants are given below.

In order to use sports hall more efficiently, the priority is to contribute more to the maintenance and repair of the problems. Keeping the halls open more by creating personnel in charge of the halls. In addition, it is thought that planning the use of the hall and especially ensuring that other schools and clubs that will use the hall use the hall continuously with a healthy planning can be realized (P1).

The views of some of the student participants are given below.

We need more time, a course doesn't help anyone (S4).

In general, we can do the following in order to use them more efficiently: Indoor games, whether it is basketball, volleyball, football, they are mostly played in outdoor areas and whether it is table tennis or volleyball training, etc., in the gym will cause us to use it more efficiently. In addition, since the physical education courses do not overlap, since the 2 classes are together, there will automatically be more people in an area and we will not be able to use this area effectively. Therefore, it will be much better if our courses do not overlap, so that we can use them more efficiently (S8).

I think that the clocks of the teams that use the gym should be adjusted more appropriately. I think that the use planning of the hall should be done well (S9).

The views of some of the teacher participants are given below.

In order for gyms to be used more efficiently, different events need to be given more space. I would also like to express my opinion that the student should be given the time and opportunity to showcase his or her talents in the gyms while the student is in school (T4).

I think this is the most important issue here, in cooperation with the municipality and using the gym cleanly at all times. I think that our school and other clubs that will use the gym will be more efficient in the operation of the hall if it is done within a program and organizes it, at what time, for what purpose, within a certain plan and program (T5).

Outside of the classroom, we can say that it can be used openly to everyone with more planned, feasible planning (T6).

When themes for suggestions for more efficient use of gyms examined in general, the views of the school principal, students and teachers on increasing the time to use the gym in order to use the gym more efficiently were mentioned more.

Discussion

In this research it was understood and interpreted the views of principals, teachers and students on the effects of gyms in schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education on students, teachers, principals and general functioning of the school. In this context, in the 2021-2022 academic year, the views of 4 school principals, 6 teachers and 9 students were obtained from the principals and teachers working in the schools with gyms in Manavgat and the students studying in these schools. This research is the first qualitative research in Turkey that aimed to determine the views of principals, teachers and students about the effects of gyms in schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education on students, teachers, principals and general functioning of the school in Turkey. Therefore, the research findings are very limited in terms of comparison with other researches. Therefore, the findings of this research were discussed by comparing them with the findings of similar two researches on this topic in Turkey.

In this research, it was found that all schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education must have a gym. It was also found out that in schools with gyms, students were better motivated to attend physical education classes. It was also revealed that physical education courses were taught better and more efficiently in schools with gyms. It can be said that the gym had a positive effect on the success of students in other subjects. Thus, it was concluded that the perceptions of school principals, students and teachers in the school gym were positive.

Similarly, according to the study conducted by Durdabak (2019), the attitudes of secondary school students in the central district of Edirne province towards physical education courses were compared according to whether there was a gym in their schools or not. As a result of the research, it was found that students in schools with gyms had a more positive attitude than students in schools without gyms. Additionally, this study found that students in schools with gyms were better motivated to attend physical education classes. It was found that physical education courses were taught better and more efficiently in schools with gyms.

In another study titled "Evaluation of the creation of a constructivist learning environment in physical education courses by teachers and students" by Elvan (2019), the views of teachers and students regarding the creation of a constructivist learning environment in physical education courses were evaluated and it was found that students who had a gym in their school had some important advantages. According to the results, it was also found that the students who had a gym had the ability to express themselves better, were able to empathize, supported positive thoughts and were able to process their courses in interaction and cooperation. These positive effects of the gym became even more evident in the courses where the constructivist learning approach was applied.

Conclusion

The first sub-problem of the research was "What are students, teachers and principals' views on gyms?". According to the findings of the research, it can be said that the views of the school principal, students and teachers in the gym were positive. It was seen that only a teacher and a student had a negative perception of the gym.

The second sub-problem of the research was "What are students, teachers and principals' views on the effect of teaching the physical education course in the gyms on the efficiency of the course?" According to the findings of the study, all of the school principal, students and teachers participants said that the effect of physical education courses in the gym on course efficiency was positive.

The third sub-problem of the research was "What are students, teachers and principals' views on the effect of the use of gyms in terms students' behaviors on the courses other than physical education class?" According to the findings of the study, the school principal and the teacher said that all of the participants said that the students' use of the gym in other courses had a positive impact on student behavior. However, half of the students said that the students' use of the gym in other classes had a positive impact on student behavior, and half of them said that it reflected negatively on student behavior.

The fourth sub-problem of the research was "What are the principals' positive or negative views on the attitudes and behaviors of the students who use the gym?" According to the findings of the study, all of the school principal participants and the majority of the student participants expressed positive views about the attitudes and behaviors of the students using the gym. However, half of the teachers said that the use of the gym reflected positively on the attitudes and behaviors of the students, but half of them said that it reflected negatively on them.

The fifth sub-problem of the research was "What are students, teachers and principals' views on the effect of gyms on school success?" According to the findings of the study, all of the school principals, students and teachers said that the effect of the gym on school success was positive.

The sixth sub-problem of the research was "What are students, teachers and principals' suggestions for more efficient use of gyms?" According to the findings of the research, the views of the school principal, students and teachers to increase the time of using the gym came to the fore in order to use the gym more efficiently.

Recommendations

In line with the findings, following suggestions were put forward:

All schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education should have a gym.

In schools with a gym, the physical capacity of the gym should be increased, the equipment deficiencies of the gym should be eliminated in a timely manner, and the time of use of the gym should be well planned and increased.

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Ethical approval

In the writing process of the study titled “**Students, teachers and principals’ views on the effects of school gyms on functioning of the school**”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the authors of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data. “Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER] and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be encountered, and all responsibility belongs to the authors and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Ethics committee approval

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 15 decision numbered 312 on September 8th, 2022.